

Local impact of load cycling on degradation in polymer electrolyte fuel cells

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Highlight 1: Impact of load cycling on PEMFC degradation studied by local current density distribution monitoring

Highlight 2: Strong Pt band formation in the membrane found in areas with high local current density

Highlight 3: Dynamic operation of PEMFC leads to lower degradation compared to steady state operation

Highlight 4: Performance losses are closely linked with inhomogeneous current density distributions

Keywords: *Polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell, automotive, dynamic load cycling, local degradation, Pt band.*

Abstract

Degradation mechanisms occurring during operation of proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFC) critically depend on the applied electrical load profile. In this work, durability tests of approximately 450 h were performed using three different load cycling ranges. The tests include shut-down and start-up events in order to recover temporary performance losses and discriminate between reversible and irreversible degradation rates. *Operando* current density distribution measurements as well as electrochemical characterization techniques were applied to obtain essential data for understanding internal degradation behavior of the components of the membrane electrode assembly (MEA). The analysis is supported by ex-situ analysis of the MEA components by scanning electron microscopy. In this study dynamic load cycling has proven to be less stressing for the MEA and lead to lower performance losses as compared to constant load operation. Among cycling experiments, the one with the highest average voltage induces highest degradation linked with increased ohmic and mass transport resistance as well as cathode thinning. Loss of electrochemical surface area is clearly detected but it does not play a key role in the performance degradation during the performed tests. In all tests reversible performance losses were associated with an increase of the heterogeneity of the current density distribution along the flow field. Ex-situ analysis shows Pt band formation in the membrane which density is correlated with local operation conditions; i.e. high local current density leads to particularly strong Pt band formation.

1. Introduction

Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells (PEMFCs) can be considered as key technology to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. One of the remaining development challenges of PEMFCs is the limited durability of membrane electrode assemblies (MEAs) caused by numerous chemical and physical degradation effects. In recent years, significant progress has been made towards meeting the challenging cost, durability, and performance targets required for the use of PEMFCs in automotive applications [1-3]

However, the currently achievable operation time is still >20% below the 2020 target [4,5]. In order to reach the durability goals, degradation of cell components has to be understood and mitigated [6-8]. Upon long-term operation all MEA components undergo physical and chemical changes leading to a reduction of the cell performance over time [8,9].

Observed degradation effects in the case of perfluorosulfonic acid membrane (PFSA) membranes and ionomers used in PEMFC are [9-15]: i) membrane thinning which leads to performance reduction due to increased hydrogen cross-over; (ii) pinhole or crack formation which results in critical cell failure; (iii) reduction of ionic conductivity due to side chain cutting of ionomer or due to blocking by non-protonic cations. Other

components prone to degradation are the electrodes where loss of electrochemically active surface area is observed due to catalyst particle growth or dissolution [16] and corrosion of the carbon support [17,18]. The gas diffusion layer (GDL) degrades by carbon corrosion and loss of hydrophobic agents like polytetrafluorethylene (PTFE) resulting in worsening of water management capabilities and gas transport properties [19].

Numerous works [10], [12], [13], [21]–[23] address MEA degradation as well as the occurring degradation processes.

Automotive PEMFC application demands dynamic load profiles which cover a broad current density range. In these profiles 100% load is usually assigned to a current density which yields around 650 mV cell voltage; i.e. a typical current density range reaches from OCV to around 1 A cm⁻². Hence, during such durability test numerous processes are involved that lead to performance losses which makes the interpretation of such tests difficult [7]. To discriminate between different phenomena, it is necessary to study certain current density ranges separately. In this study the activation region (0.0 to 0.2 A cm⁻²) and the ohmic region (0.2 to 1.0 A cm⁻²) of the performance curve have been studied separately regarding their impact on degradation in case of dynamic operation. For the sake of completeness, additional tests at constant current have been carried out to allow comparison between dynamic and constant operation. The performed experiments include in-situ local current density distribution measurements using DLR's segmented cell that has been successfully used to study local processes in PEMFC during the last years [23-28]. The investigations performed with the segmented cell were crucial to understand important aspects of a water management [29-37], contamination and durability [38,39] as well as fuel starvation [40-43]. Data obtained using the segmented cells also yield valuable information to study and evaluate the influence of cell components such a GDL, membrane and catalyst layers on cell performance [44-48]. Load cycling was studied by using different load profiles, such as square wave potential perturbations or constant high potential phases and triangular wave potential perturbations, in the literature [49]–[53]. Since square wave is considered as most relevant for an automotive dynamic load profile, in this work, square wave profiles are used to understand the aging processes that occur during load cycling, revealing the local nature of the degradation processes and linking the local changes in the current distributions with physical properties changes.

2. Experimental details

The effect of load cycling on degradation was studied in a single cell with 5x5 cm² active area and a gold coated single channel serpentine flow field arranged in co-flow configuration. The cell and the test bench were developed in-house at the German Aerospace Center (DLR).

The test bench is equipped with programmable logic controllers (PLCs) and commercial electronic loads. The gas mass flow rates were regulated at the cell inlets whereas the pressure was controlled at the cell outlets. The absolute cell outlet pressure was fixed for the experiment at a constant value of 1500 mbar. The relative humidity of 50% of the feed gases was set by adjusting the dew point temperatures of the bubbler humidifiers at 64°C and keeping the cell temperature at 80°C. The inlet gases were kept at temperatures 5°C higher than cell temperature in order to avoid water condensation.

The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and cyclic voltammetry (CV) was conducted using a PP241 potentiostat in a ZAHNER ZENNIUM electrochemical workstation with THALES software.

The current densities distributions were monitored using DLR's printed circuit board (PCB) [54], [55]. The segmentation of the PCB (segmented cell) with integrated flow field placed at the anode side is depicted in Figure 1 (A). This board is divided in 49 segments, each one with an integrated current sensor and with a total of 6 integrated temperature sensors.

The MEAs used in this study consisted of commercial MEA0476 catalyst coated membranes (CCMs) from Johnson Matthey Fuel Cells® and Sigracet 25 BC gas diffusion layers (GDL) from SGL Carbon GmbH. The cells were sealed with Ice Cube sealing from Freudenberg®.

Testing protocols and electrochemical characterization

Once assembled, the cells were submitted to the protocol illustrated in Figure 1 (B) consisting of:

- Breaking-in:

Starting up the cell to nominal operation conditions (80°C, 50%RH, 1.5 bar, 1.5(anode)/2.0(cathode) stoichiometry) and monitoring cell voltage and current density distribution at 1 A cm⁻² for 1 hour. After 1h, the voltage stabilized, and the current density distribution becomes homogenous and the cell was considered ready for performance and durability testing.

Figure 1 – (A) Segmented single channel serpentine flow field. The labels of columns A-G and rows 1-7 are coordinates of the individual segments. Gas inlet is placed in the segment G1 and the gas outlet is located in A7 marked with arrows (B) Schematized representation of one test block.

- BoT and EoT characterization:

After break-in, the cell was submitted to a first set of electrochemical measurements defined as beginning of test (BoT) characterization. The same characterization techniques were applied at end of test (EoT) as a last step of the testing protocol.

The performance curve was measured starting at OCV and then increasing the current density up to 1.8 A cm^{-2} . In the current density range $0.0\text{--}0.2 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$ the gas flows at anode and cathode were constant at 53 and 166 m min^{-1} , respectively. Above 0.2 A cm^{-2} the respective gas flows were kept at fixed stoichiometries of 1.5 and 2.0 . The BoT cell performance is provided in Figure 2.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements were performed in galvanostatic mode, under constant loads of 0.1 and 0.6 A cm^{-2} with a frequency range from 100 mHz to 100 kHz and an amplitude of the perturbation of 0.02 A cm^{-2} . The test electrode was fed with hydrogen while the counter electrode was fed with air, according to respective stoichiometries of 1.5 and 2.0 .

Cyclic voltammetry measurements were conducted for both anode and cathode. Nitrogen (100 ml min^{-1}) was passed through the test electrode and hydrogen (50 ml min^{-1}) was passed through the counter electrode. Five cycles were performed in the potential range from 60 mV to 1 V at a sweep rate of 20 mV s^{-1} . The starting point of each cycle was at 400 mV . Relative humidity of the feed gases was set to 100% by increasing the temperature of the bubblers to $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

- Durability testing:

Once fully characterized, the MEA proceeds to durability testing, which consists of three periods of continuous PEMFC operation using the protocols provided in Figure 2 interrupted by refresh procedures in order to recover reversible voltage losses. Each period was targeted to last approximately 140 hours. The refresh procedure corresponds to shutting down the test bench (shut down electrical load, stop gas supply, release pressure, stop heating) for a period of approx. 12 hours. After the durability test periods and a final recovery procedure the EoT characterization was performed.

Figure 2: Left: Load cycling profiles applied in this study. Right: Ranges of load cycles related to the BoT performance curve of the tested MEA.

Ex-situ characterization

Analyses of the freeze-fractured MEAs were performed using a JEOL JSM7200F, equipped with a Bruker Quantax energy dispersive X-ray analysis detector, scanning electron microscope (SEM) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). On the SEM holder they were stabilized and electrically connected with double-sided conductive adhesive tape. The platinum content was analyzed as surface area fraction of the backscatter electron detector (BSE) images using the software ImageJ.

3. Results and Discussion

In order to study the impact of load cycling on degradation mechanisms, three different ranges of load cycles were tested to cover the nominal operation range of a PEMFC (see Figure 2):

- Cycling 1 (Cycling in the activation region): load variation between 10 s at OCV and 10 s at $0.2\ A\ cm^{-2}$,
- Cycling 2 (cycling in the ohmic region of the performance curve): load variation between 10s at $0.2\ A\ cm^{-2}$ and $1\ A\ cm^{-2}$,
- Cycling 3 (cycling in the entire nominal operation range of the PEMFC): load variation between 10s at OCV and $1\ A\ cm^{-2}$.

Figure 3 (Left) shows the voltage evolution measured for the three load cycles tested. In all cases the transition time between load levels was 1s.

Maximum applied current density in the cycling experiments is 1 Acm^{-2} which corresponds to 650 mV cell voltage which is a typical value for nominal automotive operation.

Additionally, Figure 3 (Right) depicts the mapping of the current density distributions recorded during the individual tests at BoT as well as before and after each refresh.

The degradation mechanisms and rates were evaluated from:

- The irreversible/reversible degradation rates calculated from the polarization curves at BoT and after each refresh.
- The ECSA losses calculated from the CV at BoT and after each refresh.
- The changes in the impedances
- The local ex-situ analysis settled due to the differences in the current distributions measured during the durability test.

Current Distribution in Durability Tests

The degradation tests performed using the three cycling protocols (Figure 3 (left)) shows decreasing cell voltage as a function of operation time. Recoverable performance losses between the end of each period and the beginning of the next one are observed. This fact suggests that the overall potential degradation comprises two kind of degradation process: one related with reversible and another with irreversible losses.

The mappings of current density distributions, measured at the beginning and the end of each period show severe changes, i.e. the current density distributions become inhomogeneous during operation. During Cycling 1 and 2 and at low currents (0.2 Acm^{-2}), performance drops were measured in the areas close to the gas inlets. This can be explained due to drying process by the high gas flows set according to the stoichiometry required at 1 Acm^{-2} which may lead to drying of the cell especially at the gas inlets. However, the current density distributions largely recover during the refresh period. The recovery is not complete, and, especially in the last test period, irreversible mechanisms gain more importance and the inhomogeneities become only partly removed. These irreversible losses are concurrent with the increase of the high and low frequencies resistances measured by EIS as will be showed in next sections.

Figure 3: (Left:) Cell voltage versus test duration recorded using the load profiles Cycling 1 (A), Cycling 2(B), and Cycling 3 (C). (Right:) Corresponding current density distributions recorded during the test at BoT, before and after each refresh and at EoT. The assignment of the acquisition time of the current density image and the test is provided by the number labels. Gas inlet and outlet of the cell is located at segment G1 and A7, respectively.

In the first two test periods of Cycling 2 and 3 at high current (1 A cm^{-2}) similar trends in the current inhomogeneities are observed. Thereby, the changes at the gas inlet reveal to be less significant at high current than at 0.2 A cm^{-2} . In the last test period, however, outlet regions exhibit performance losses, most probably due to the starvation processes at higher currents caused by the one channel serpentine flow field and a non-optimum gas distribution.

Determination of Degradation Rates

The performance curves have been measured for the three cycling tests at BoT, before and after each refresh as well as at EoT. The corresponding data is plotted in Figure 1S in the supporting information. The irreversible degradation rates (voltage loss per time) have been calculated from the performance curves at BoT and after each refresh. This allows the determination of degradation rates as a function of current density as shown in Figure 4 (A). Additionally, corresponding irreversible degradation rates from two tests conducted at a constant current density of 0.1 and 1.0 A cm^{-2} (data is not

shown; the tests consist of three periods of operation interrupted by analogous recovery procedure as used with the cycling tests) are added. Apparently, the irreversible degradation rates of the cycling tests are significantly lower than of the constant load tests. Moreover, the increased irreversible degradation is observed for the entire current density range. This can be explained comparing the BoT and EoT impedance spectra which will be discussed in the next section. Among the cycling tests it is Cycling 1 which exhibits significantly higher degradation than Cycling 2 and Cycling 3 and which includes operation at high potentials only.

Figure 4: (A) Irreversible degradation rates calculated from the performance curves at BoT and after each refresh taking into account the operation time at which the performance curves were measured. Additionally, irreversible degradation rates from two tests conducted at a constant current density of 0.1 and 1.0 A cm^{-2} are added. (B) Differential resistance calculated from the performance curves at 0.08 and 1.0 A cm^{-2} .

In order to visualize the reversibility of the degradation in the cycling tests, the differential resistances have been calculated from the U-I curves at 1 A cm^{-2} and 0.08 A cm^{-2} representative for the ohmic and the activation region of the performance curves, respectively. The differential resistances evaluated at BoT, before and after each refresh are depicted in Figure 4 (B). The resistance at 1 A cm^{-2} slightly and continuously increase with test duration; the strongest increase, which is consistent with the high degradation rate, is observed for Cycling 1. The increase of the differential

resistance at 1 Acm^{-2} corresponds to an increase of ohmic losses of the MEA which are related to increasing membrane and interfacial resistances. More pronounced differences between Cycling 1 and Cycling 2 and 3 occur at 0.08 Acm^{-2} : for Cycling 1 a strong increase of differential resistance in the activation region develops during each operation period. This effect is partly reversible since the refresh procedures are clearly linked with a reduction of this resistance. Consequently, Cycling 1 leads to severe reversible degradation in the activation region of the U-I curve likely related to temporal catalyst passivation.

Electrochemical characterization

CVs measurements of the anodes and cathodes of the samples have been recorded at BoT and after each refresh to determine the ECSA from the H_2 desorption peak. The results in Figure 5 (A) show relative ECSA losses between BoT and EoT. Apparently, the relative ECSA losses are much stronger on the cathodes than on the anodes which is due to the higher cathode potential. Interestingly, the ECSA losses of the constant operation tests are lower than of the cycling test even though the degradation rates of the MEAs operated at constant loads were much higher. Hence, ECSA loss cannot be considered as a main reason for the observed performance degradation but could be an important issue for longer operation times when the the ECSA decrease to critical levels. It is noted that the observed ECSA loss is not just an effect of the breaking-in of the MEAs that usually occurs during the first operation hours, but the decrease of ECSA is a continuous process as evidenced by Figure S2 in the supporting information. One mechanism of the cathodic ECSA loss is platinum dissolution and migration from the cathode to the membrane that will be discussed later. In some cases, the precipitation and growth of platinum in the anode side may be the reason for the minimal relative catalyst loss on this side [56].

Figure 5: (A) Relative changes of anode and cathode ECSA between BoT and EoT. (B) Low frequency and high frequency resistance changes between the BoT and the EoT for the different samples. Intersection with the real axis in the Nyquist diagrams at high and low frequencies EIS measurements were performed at 0.6 A cm^{-2} .

With the purpose of evaluating the resistances due to different degradation process of the tested cells, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy was performed at 0.6 A cm^{-2} after each refresh period. Figure 5 (B) shows the relative increase of the high and low frequency resistances between BoT and EoT determined from the intercept of the Nyquist diagrams with the real impedance axis at low and high frequency (see in Figure 3S in the supporting information). Cycling 1 shows a clear growth in the ohmic resistance between BoT and EoT (approx. 12%) but negligible differences (<1%) were measured for Cycling 2 and 3. This observation can be linked with the irreversible degradation rates. Severe damage in the membrane will be reflected in a high ohmic resistances producing irreversible degradation as was observed in the constant current experiments. On the contrary, large differences were measured between BoT and EoT at low frequencies, especially remarkable during Cycling 1. In this case the relatively high cell voltage during Cycling 1 induces carbon corrosion in the catalyst layer as well in the porous media on the cathode side. The corrosion of the carbon media has particularly high impact when the cell is operated at high currents where proper gas supply and removal of product water play major roles regarding the cell performance. Once the carbon structure is degraded the cell suffers due to increased mass transport resistance. This finding agrees with the results shown in Figure 4A; i.e. increase of the

high frequency resistance correlates well with the irreversible degradation rates observed at high current densities. However, the sensitivity to voltage losses is of course higher at high current density due to larger voltage drop. Therefore the differential resistance in the ohmic region should be compared (see Cycling 1 at 1 A cm^{-2} in Figure 4 (B)) yielding an increase by 150-200 $\text{m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ between BoT and EoT.

Local degradation analysis

To evaluate the structural degradation of the cycled cells, selected segments (see Figure 6 (A)) have been cut out of the MEAs after EoT for SEM analysis. With SEM, especially when using the backscattered electron detector (BSD), heavy elements give more signals relative to the amount of incident electrons and appear brighter in the image compared to light elements. Freeze-fractured MEAs of all analyzed samples from the cycling and constant load tests showed platinum particles in the membrane. The platinum re-deposits were detected close to the cathode side as shown in Figure 6 (B) as an example. The platinum content in front of the cathode was analyzed at areas of $15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^2$ provided Figure 6 (E). It is known from literature [57], [58] that in fuel cell operation due to numerous reasons (temperature, particle size, pH and potential), platinum dissolves even at lower potentials than expected from the stability limit given in the pourbaix diagram of Pt. The dissolved platinum diffuses/migrates across the membrane and can be reduced to Pt by hydrogen that permeates through the membrane from the anode side. The position of the platinum inside the membrane is thus defined by the partial pressures of hydrogen and oxygen which determines the local potential inside the membrane [59]. For proving that the particles visible in the images are platinum, EDX mapping (see Figure 6 (C)), EDX spectrum analysis (Figure 4S in the supporting information) and EDX Pt line-scans (Figure 4S in the supporting information) were recorded. A higher magnification of the platinum particles is shown in Figure 6 (D). A difference in the size of the particles was detected with the smallest particles in the segments after operation protocol Cycling 2. The redeposited particles formed spherical agglomerates or a crystal structure. Dendrite growth occurred at bigger particles as shown in Figure 6 (D) and Figure 6S in the supporting information. It should be noted that due to the limited resolution in the SEM images very small particles cannot be detected but might be present. Interestingly, in segment A5 of the Cycling 3 test also platinum particles are detected in the membrane at the anode side (not shown).

Figure 6: (A) Sketch of the segments analyzed by SEM within the segmented MEA. (B) Large area SEM BSE image of freeze fractured MEA at segment A5 after Cycling 1. (C) EDX Pt mapping at segment A5 after Cycling 1. (D) Higher magnification of the Pt particles at segment A5 after Cycling 1. (E) Binarized SEM BSE images of the Pt-band (Pt visible as white spots) in segments A5, D5 and G5 after the individual cycling tests.

The results of the average platinum area fraction of the image measured in front of the cathode are shown in Figure 7 with the standard error of the mean of six areas. The platinum area fraction taken as a measure for the Pt content is comparably high after operation with Cycling 1 and Cycling 3. The platinum content measured in the MEA after operation with Cycling 2 is considerably less than for the two other MEAs. Cycling 2 protocol did not include OCV condition which is known to be harsher for the stability of the Pt and carbon corrosion in the electrodes. The platinum content in the segments follows the same order for all MEAs: The highest Pt content was always measured at segments A5, less at segments D5 and the lowest content at G5 segments.

Figure 7: Top: Current density distributions of Cycling 1 (measured at 0.2 Acm^{-2} before 3^{rd} refresh), Cycling 2 (measured at 0.2 Acm^{-2} before 2^{nd} refresh), and Cycling 3 (measured at 1 Acm^{-2} before 3^{rd} refresh). The color scale corresponds to current density increasing from blue to red. Bottom: Average platinum area fraction in front of the cathodes (six measurements with $15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^2$ each at the membrane in front of the cathode), error bars indicate the standard error of the mean for 6 measurements. The analyzed segments are indicated by the black squares in the current density distribution images at the top of the figure.

Comparing the current density measured in the analyzed segments in Figure 7 (top) recorded during the cycling tests reported in Figure 3 suggests a trend: the higher the local current density during operation the more Pt is detected in the membrane. This is clearly valid for Cycling 1 and Cycling 2. In Cycling 3 the trend is less clear. Further analysis has been performed by correlating the current density distributions obtained from the polarization curves with the amount of Pt determined in the corresponding segment. The data shows that with higher local current density a higher amount of Pt in the membrane was found (see Figure 5S in the supporting information). For lower current densities, no corresponding correlation was found.

Figure 8: Thicknesses of electrode components determined from SEM cross sections. (A) Thickness of the cathode at investigated segments before and after operation, the error bars indicate the standard error of the mean for 6 measurements. (B) Thickness of the anode at investigated segments before and after operation, the error bars indicate the standard error of the mean for 6 measurements.

The thickness of the cathodes at the different segments decreased for MEAs that were operated with OCV included in the protocol, i.e. MEAs of Cycling 1 and Cycling 3 (see Figure 8 (A)). The decrease of cathode thickness after operation was largest after operation mode Cycling 1 and Cycling 3 at segments A5, where the highest amount of platinum was measured in the membrane (compare Figure 7). The change in cathode thickness of Cycling 2 is not significant.

The MEAs after the operation protocols Cycling 1 and Cycling 2 showed no significant thickness change of the anodes. Only the anode of the MEA after Cycling 3 test shows a clear decrease of the thickness (Figure 8 (B)). These observations harmonize with the fact, that only for the MEA of Cycling 3 platinum was detected in the membrane close to the anode side. The decrease of the anode thickness could be due to chemical degradation catalyzed by the Pt and/or by carbon corrosion.

4. Conclusions

The impact of load cycling on PEMFC degradation was studied through the performance of three durability tests with different current ranges of operation (0.0-0.2 Acm⁻², 0.2-1.0 Acm⁻² and 0.0-1.0 Acm⁻²). The results were additionally compared with tests performed at steady state conditions.

The results clearly show that dynamic operation, such as required in automotive conditions, leads to lower performance losses compared to operation at constant current. Among the cycling tests, the one with operation in the low current range (i.e. high potential range) exhibited highest irreversible and reversible degradation which is caused by a significantly increased ohmic and mass transport resistance. The

observed performance losses are closely linked with inhomogeneous current density distributions. These inhomogeneities are partly reversible. Nevertheless, the regions that experience relatively high local current densities develop a platinum band in the membrane which is correlated with irreversible cathode degradation. Since Pt redeposited in the membrane is known to accelerate membrane [13, 60] degradation, the results suggest that maintaining a homogenous current density distribution during operation is beneficial or even necessary to avoid local degradation issues. The measured ECSA losses are not clearly related to performance losses (e.g. cycling tests lead to much higher ECSA loss even though constant load test which have higher degradation lead to relatively low ECSA losses). However, since the ECSA reduction develops continuously with operation time, it is likely that after long term operation these losses become critical especially on the cathode.

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